

1 Identification and Quantification of Metallo-Chlorophyll Complexes in Bright Green Table Olives by
2 High-Performance Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry Quadrupole/Time-of-Flight

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8 ABSTRACT:

9 Five different samples of table olives, two regular Spanish table olives and three “bright green table
10 olives”, have been analyzed by HPLC-MS/MS to determine their pigment profile. Typical pigment
11 profiles of almost all table olives show primarily chlorophyll derivatives lacking metals (e.g.,
12 pheophytin *a/b* and 15²-Me-phytol-chlorin *e*₆). Bright green table olives have a unique profile
13 including metallo-chlorophyll complexes (Cu-15²-Me-phytol-chlorin *e*₆ with 26-48% and Cu-
14 pheophytin *a* with 3-18%) as their major pigments. New tentative structures have been identified by
15 MS such as 15²-Me-phytol-rhodin *g*₇, 15²-Me-phytol-chlorin *e*₆, 15²-Me-phytol-isochlorin *e*₄, Cu-15²-
16 -Me-phytol-rhodin *g*₇, Cu-15²-Me-phytol-chlorin *e*₆, and Cu-15²-Me-phytol-isochlorin *e*₄, and new
17 MS/MS fragmentation patterns are reported for Cu-15²-Me-phytol-rhodin *g*₇, Cu-15²-Me-phytol-
18 chlorin *e*₆, Cu-pheophytin *b*, Cu-pheophytin *a*, Cu-pyropheophytin *b*, and Cu-pyropheophytin *a*. The
19 presence of metallo-chlorophyll derivatives is responsible for the intense color of bright green table
20 olives, but these metallo-chlorophyll complexes may be regarded as a “green staining” defect that is
21 unacceptable to consumers.

22 KEYWORDS: high-performance liquid chromatography, mass spectrometry, table olives, Cu-
23 pheophytin, metallo-chlorophylls, green staining alteration, regreening.

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27 INTRODUCTION

28 The color of vegetable products is one of the most important sensory attributes evaluated by
29 consumers worldwide, and, in green fresh vegetables and fruits, the green color is due to the presence
30 of chlorophylls *a* and *b*. For table olives, color is a very critical attribute. The most common color
31 changes of fresh vegetables during cooking, freeze preservation, storage, or heat processing are due
32 to the conversion of chlorophylls (*a* and *b*), responsible for bright green color, into their respective
33 pheophytins (*a* and *b*) that are responsible for yellow-brown olive color. This dramatic change in color
34 involves the release of the magnesium from the porphyrin ring. However, the insertion of metals
35 within the porphyrin ring, such as zinc (Zn²⁺) or copper (Cu²⁺), produces a regreening effect. These
36 metallo-chlorophyll complexes are more stable, due to higher metal-porphyrin bond energies, and
37 more resistant to acid and heat than are naturally occurring magnesium (Mg²⁺) chlorophyll
38 complexes.¹ In addition, the formation of copper complexes is much more rapid than zinc
39 complexes.^{2,3} Regreening via the formation of metallo-chlorophyll complexes has been used to
40 preserve the desirable fresh green color of vegetables by the food industry,^{4,5} including several
41 patents.⁴⁻⁷ In the traditional processing of Spanish style of table olives, chlorophylls *a* and *b* are
42 degraded completely to pheophytins and pheophorbides during the fermentation process by two
43 different and coexisting mechanisms. In the initial treatment of the olives with NaOH, at alkaline pH,

44 the chlorophyllase is active, but in the fermentation process, pH turns acidic followed by the loss of
45 Mg^{2+} . The pigment transformation brought about by lactic fermentation produces olives that are
46 highly valuable for their characteristic golden color.⁸ The innovations introduced in the traditional
47 system of processing (elimination of the short washing, addition of acids, reuse of brines, etc.) have
48 changed the previously described mechanism of chlorophyll degradation, with the detection of
49 oxidative reactions that affects the chlorophyll isocyclic ring and production of allomerized
50 chlorophylls.⁹

51 Nevertheless, the Gordal variety, used almost exclusively to produce table olives, develops an
52 alteration in color, known as “green staining” (GS) that is undesirable to consumers.¹⁰ This common
53 defect is observed as bluish-green zones distributed over the skin that contrasts with its natural olive
54 color. This alteration most likely occurs through the formation of endogenous metal porphyrin
55 complexes to create GS.¹¹ The formation of metallo-chlorophyll complexes is thought to arise from
56 the fruit’s endogenous Cu and may involve degradation of cell integrity allowing contact of the metal
57 with the chlorophyll derivatives, which under normal conditions are protected in their natural
58 lipophilic environment. Endogenous metal such as Cu may arise from the pectin chain that can serve
59 as a reservoir of copper that is captured by chlorophyll pigments separated from the thylakoid
60 membrane to form the copper chlorophyll complexes.¹² The most common technique to analyze these
61 pigments is RP-HPLC-DAD, although HPLC-MS has also been employed for the determination of
62 chlorophylls and their derivatives because it provides structural information, and, in addition, it is a
63 very sensitive and selective technique. Methods based on HPLC-MS include atmospheric pressure
64 ionization (APCI)^{13,14} and electrospray ionization (ESI)^{15,16} interfaces. Previously, GS alteration has been
65 studied,^{8,11} although those studies did not utilize HPLC-MS and tandem MS with accurate mass as an
66 identification tool. In this study, metallo-chlorophyll complexes responsible for green staining are
67 identified by HPLC mass spectrometry and quantified by HPLC in three commercial samples. In
68 addition, their pigment profiles are compared to typical table olives (yellow-brown olive color).

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70 MATERIALS AND METHODS

71 Samples. The study was carried out with five different commercial green table olives bought at
72 different markets: sample A, “Italian Castelvetrano Whole Green Olives” (product of Italy) packed by
73 Mezzetta Inc.; sample B, “Olives Castelvetrano Divina” packed by Whole Foods Market; sample C,
74 “Green Table Olives” packed by Vincenzo’s; sample D, “Spanish Olives” (var. Manzanilla); and sample
75 E, “Spanish Queen Olives” (var. Gordal) (both Spanish products) distributed by Kroger Co.

76 Chemicals and Standards. Ammonium acetate was supplied by Fluka (Zwijndrecht, The Netherlands).
77 HPLC/MS and HPLC reagent grade solvents were purchased from Fisher Scientific Inc. (Pittsburgh, PA).
78 Standards of pheophorbide *a*, Cu-pheophorbide *a*, rhodoin *g*₇, chlorin *e*₆, and Cu-chlorin *e*₆ were
79 supplied by Porphyrin Product Inc. (Logan, UT). Chlorophylls *a* (chl *a*) and *b* (chl *b*) were supplied by
80 Sigma-Aldrich Co. (St. Louis, MO). Standards of pheophytin *a* (phy *a*) and *b* (phy *b*) were obtained from
81 their respective chlorophyll by acidification.¹⁷ Standards of Cu-pheophytin *a* and *b* were obtained from
82 their respective chlorophyll by reaction with an excess of copper(II) ions as chloride.¹⁰

83 Extraction of Pigments. Fifty depitted fruits (ca. 40 g) were ground and homogenized. Triplicate
84 extractions were prepared by accurately weighing 5-15 g for each sample. Pigment extraction was
85 performed with N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF), according to the method proposed by Mínguez-
86 Mosquera and Garrido-Fernandez¹⁸ that allows the selective separation of pigments in oil free
87 pigment solutions. Thus, DMF retains chlorophyll and xanthophylls, while the hexane phase retains
88 the carotene fraction. All of the analytical procedures were performed under red lighting to avoid any
89 photooxidation of the chlorophyllic compounds.

90 HPLC-MS and HPLC-MS/MS. HPLC-MS analysis was carried out on a Waters 2695 gradient HPLC
91 separation module (Waters Corp., Milford, MA) equipped with an auto injector and a 996-photodiode
92 array detector (PDA). Chromatographic separations were performed on a HALO C18 Symmetry column
93 (75 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 2.7 μm) (MAC-MOD Analytical, Inc.). The mobile phase consisted of (1/1/8)
94 (v/v/v) water/ammonium acetate 1 M/methanol (solvent A), acetonitrile (solvent B), and reagent
95 alcohol (solvent C) at a flow rate of 1.25 mL/min. Column temperature was kept at 25 °C. Table 1
96 shows the gradient scheme for eluting the pigments.

97 Mass spectrometric studies were performed on a Quadrupole/ time-of-flight mass spectrometer
98 (QToF Premier, Micromass Limited, Manchester, U.K.) equipped with an atmospheric pressure
99 chemical ionization interface (APCI). Positive ion APCI conditions for chlorophyll analyses were: 30 μA
100 corona current, collision energy 8 eV, cone voltage 35 V, source temperature at 110 °C, 50 L/h of cone
101 gas, and the flow of nitrogen desolvation gas was 400 L/h, at 450 °C. Daughter ions spectra were
102 obtained by APCI negative using various collision energies (8-35 eV). Sodium formate solution was
103 used to calibrate the mass spectrometer from m/z 100-1500 with mass accuracy of <2 ppm. Detection
104 and tentative identification of all of the chlorophyll derivatives were accomplished using in-line
105 electronic absorption spectra recorded every 1.2 nm from 200 to 800 nm with a Waters model 996-
106 PDA (Milford, MA). Quantification of all of the chlorophyll derivatives was based on PDA data from
107 calibration curves with external standards at the respective λ_{max} of each compound.

108 Color Measurement. The color analysis has been made with a Minolta colorimeter (CR-300) using CIE
109 $L^*a^*b^*$ scale with illuminants C.

110 Statistical Analysis. Data were analyzed for differences between means using one-way analysis of
111 variance (ANOVA). The Brown and Forsythe test¹⁹ was used as a post hoc comparison of statistical
112 significance (p values < 0.05) using Statistica 6.0 (StatSoft, Inc., 2001)

113

114 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

115 As color is the variable that should distinguish bright green table olives from regular table olives with
116 a yellow-brown olive color, a Minolta colorimeter using CIE Lab scale was used.

117 Figure 1 displays $L^*a^*b^*$ values of all of the samples showing that bright green table olives are
118 statistically different (p values < 0.05) from the regular table olives with all of the coordinates ($-8.4 \pm$
119 2.6 vs -2.6 ± 0.3), with coordinate a^* (a^* , negative values indicate green, while positive values indicate
120 magenta) being the most remarkable. In addition, there are no statistical differences (p values < 0.05)
121 in $L^*a^*b^*$ coordinates within the samples of the two sets.

122 Once it was established that color was a determinant variable distinguishing the two sets of samples,
123 the chemical compounds responsible for the color difference were identified and quantified by HPLC-
124 MS/MS. Thus, Figure 2 shows the HPLC chromatograms, recorded at 650 nm, of chlorophylls,
125 chlorophyll derivatives, and metallo-chlorophylls complexes (Table 2) determined in the five samples
126 studied. Table 3 lists all of the pigments identified in Figure 2 with their chromatographic,
127 spectroscopic, and mass characteristics. The information from the spectral data agrees basically with
128 the published information. Although many of these pigments observed herein have been identified
129 20-22 by mass spectrometry, nine pigment components (peaks numbered 6, 7, 9, 11, 15, 19, 22, 23,
130 and 26) were not yet characterized by MS/MS.

131 Pigment profiles presented in Figure 2 show that bright green table olive samples (A, Castelvetro-
132 Mezzetta; B, Vincenzo's; C, Castelvetro-WF) can be easily distinguished from Spanish table olives
133 (D, var. Gordal; E, var. Manzanilla).

134 The chromatograms of the samples coded A-C showed the highest concentrations of Cu-15² -Me-
135 phytol-chlorin e₆ ester (peak 11), Cu-pheophytin *a* (peaks 22-23), Cu-pyropheophytin *a* (peak 26), and
136 chlorophylls *a* (peaks 12-13) and *b* (peaks 8 and 10).

137 Concerning the other two samples (coded D,E), the more representative compounds are pheophytin
138 *a* (peaks 18 and 21) and *b* (peaks 14 and 16), 15² -Me-phytol-rhodin g₇ ester (peak 6), and 15² -Me-
139 phytol-chlorin e₆ ester (peak 9), although minor pigments, such as pheophorbide *a* (peak 1) and
140 pyropheophorbide *a* (peak 3), are also present. The most characteristic of the chlorophyll pigments in
141 the Spanish style olive, processed by fermentation, is that all of the chlorophyll pigments have lost
142 magnesium within the porphyrin ring, resulting in table olives with a yellow-brown olive color.

143 However, allomerized chlorophyll compounds detected in the Spanish style of table olives were
144 identified primarily as phytol-chlorin e₆ and phytol-rhodin g₇ from their chromatographic
145 characteristics and absorption spectral data.⁹ Subsequently, the nominal mass molecular ion obtained
146 by MS led to its identification as 15-glyoxilic acid pheophytin *a* and 15-glyoxilic acid pheophytin *b*,
147 compounds with similar chromatographic and spectral characteristics but different molecular mass.⁸
148 Finally, accurate mass MS/MS data from the ion fragmentation obtained in this work suggested a new
149 structure such as 15² -Me-phytol-rhodin g₇ ester (peak 6) and 15² -Me-phytol-chlorin e₆ ester (peak 9).

150 These pigments could be obtained by solvolysis of the isocyclic ring of the respective pheophytin
151 according to the reaction scheme given by Hyninen.²³

152 From the set of newly identified pigments, the most abundant in bright green table olives were Cu-
153 15² -Me-phytol-rhodin g₇ ester, Cu-15² -Me-phytol-chlorin e₆ ester, Cu-pheophytin *a*, and Cu-
154 pyropheophytin *a*, and also 15² -Me-phytol-rhodin g₇ ester and 15² -Me-phytol-chlorin e₆ ester in the
155 Spanish table olives. The MS/MS fragmentation patterns of the first two pigments, using a ramped
156 collision energy, revealed the following daughter ions (Figures 3 and 4): *m/z* 918.5, 886.4, 568.2, and
157 536.1 for Cu-15² -Me-phytol-rhodin g₇ ester ([M - H]⁻ = 964.5) and 904.5, 872.5, 554.2, and 522.1 for
158 Cu-15² -Me-phytol-chlorin e₆ ester ([M - H]⁻ = 948.5). The ions 918.5 and 904.4 are consistent with the
159 loss of a carboxylic group (M-CO₂) from the respective molecular ion, while the loss of a methoxy
160 group (M-CH₃O-H) from ions 918.5 and 904.4 would yield ions with *m/z* 886.4 and 872.5, respectively.
161 Similarly, the loss of the phytol ester chain (M-CH₂CH₂COO-phytyl) from 886.4, 872.5, 918.5, and 904.4
162 would yield ions *m/z* 536.1, 522.1, 568.2, and 554.2, respectively. These pigments have been identified
163 before as Cu-15-glyoxilic acid pheophytins *a* and *b*, respectively.¹¹

164 However, these pigments differ from the new structures identified herein due to a glyoxilic acid (-
165 COCOOH) in R₄ (Table 4). No fragment such as M-CO or M-COCOOH has been found for the new
166 structures, allowing the possibility of phytol-rhodin or phytol-chlorin structures. The MS/MS
167 fragmentation patterns of Cu-pheophytin *a* and its epimer *a'* using a fixed collision energy of 30 eV
168 are shown in Figures 5 and 6. Both epimers yielded the same fragmentation patterns: the loss of phytol
169 yielding the fragment 652.2 (M-phytyl), the loss of the phytol ester chain yielding the mass 580.2 (M-
170 CH₂CH₂COO-phytyl), the loss of the phytol chain (M-O-phytyl) plus the loss of the methoxy carbonyl
171 group (M-COOCH₃) of R₄ yields the mass 576.2, and the loss of the methyl group from the
172 methoxycarbonyl group of R₄ yields the mass 565.1. However, the abundance of fragment ions is
173 different for Cu-pheophytin *a* and its respective epimer under identical conditions. A similar
174 observation has been reported previously with pheophytins *a* and *b*.²⁰ The Cu-pheophytin *a* epimer
175 exhibited an abundant fragment of 580.2 (M-CH₂CH₂COO-Phytyl), approximately 10% greater than for
176 *a*, whereas the fragment *m/z* 576.2 occurred with minor intensity.

177 Table 4 shows MS/MS fragmentation patterns of 15² -Me-phytol-rhodin g₇ ester and 15² -Me-phytol-
178 chlorin e₆ ester using fixed collision energy of 15 eV. The ions with *m/z* 857.6 and 843.6 represent the
179 loss of a carboxylic group from the respective molecular ion, while the loss of a methoxy group from

180 ions 857.6 and 843.6 yields the ions 825.5 and 811.6, respectively. The loss of the phytyl ester chain
181 from 825.5, 811.6, 857.6, and 843.6 yields the ions 475.2, 461.2, 507.2, and 493.2, respectively. MS/
182 MS fragmentation patterns of Cu-pyropheophytin *a* used a fixed collision energy of 30 eV. The loss of
183 phytyl yielded the fragment 594.2 (M-phytyl), the loss of the carboxy phytyl yielded the mass 550.2
184 (M-COO-phytyl), and the loss of the phytyl ester chain yielded the mass 522.2 (M-CH₂CH₂COO-phytyl).
185 Less relevant due to their low concentration in bright green table olives are Cu-pheophytin *b* and Cu-
186 pyropheophytin *b*. The MS/ MS fragmentation pattern of Cu-pheophytin *b* is 945.5 and of Cu-
187 pyropheophytin *b* is 887.5. The main daughter fragments obtained for Cu-pheophytin *b* (Table 4) are
188 666.2 (M-phytyl) and 590.1 due to the loss of -COO-phytyl and -COOCH₃ of the R₄, while the main
189 fragments obtained for Cu-pyropheophytin *b* (Table 4) are 608.1 (M-phytyl), 564.2 (M-COO-phytyl),
190 and 536.1 (M-CH₂CH₂COO-phytyl).

191 In regard to 15²-Me-phytol-isochlorin *e*₄ and Cu-15²-Me-phytol-isochlorin *e*₄, these compounds were
192 identified previously as formylpheophytin *a* and its Cu derivative by their respective molecular
193 ions.^{11,27} However, both mass accurate m/z values obtained herein are consistent with a structure with
194 a -CH₂COOCH₃ group in R₄ and -H in R₅ (15²-Me-phytol-isochlorin *e*₄ and Cu-15²-Me-phytol-isochlorin
195 *e*₄, respectively) or with an ethyl group (-CH₂CH₃) and a carboxylic group (-COOH) in R₅ (15²-Et-phytol-
196 chlorin *e*₄ and Cu-15²-Et-phytol-chlorin *e*₄, respectively) (Table 4). The two first options (15²-Me-
197 phytol-isochlorin *e*₄ and Cu-15²-Me-phytol-isochlorin *e*₄) are more likely to occur from the loss of the
198 carboxylic group of the respective chlorin *e*₆. Nevertheless, we could not acquire an appropriate
199 MS/MS fragmentation pattern for these pigments that gave us a confident identification. Further
200 MS/MS characterization is needed.

201 The quantitative analysis of the pigments present in the table olive samples (Figure 7) shows that the
202 range of concentrations of the major pigments of bright green table olives were Cu-15²-Me-phytol-
203 chlorin *e*₆ ester (26-48%), Cu-15²-Me-phytol-rhodin *g*₇ ester (2-18%), Cu-pheophytin *a* (3-18%),
204 pheophytin *a* (0-18%), Cu-pyropheophytin *a* (1-5%), chlorophyll *a* (0-6%), 15²-Me-phytol-rhodin *g*₇
205 ester (1-2%), and chlorophyll *b* (0-2%). The major pigments present in the Spanish table olives, in terms
206 of concentration, were pheophytin *a* (36-37%), pheophytin *b* (13-20%), 15²-Me-phytol-chlorin *e*₆ ester
207 (17-29%), and 15²-Me-phytol-rhodin *g*₇ ester (8-15%).

208 The relative amount of various chlorophyll derivatives, with or without metal within the porphyrin
209 ring, allows differentiation among the samples. Thus, Figure 8 shows the percent of Cu-metallo-
210 chlorophylls (T Cu), Mg-metallo-chlorophylls (T Mg), chlorophylls without magnesium (T-Mg), Cu-
211 metallo-chlorophylls plus Mg-metallo-chlorophylls (T Cu+Mg), and an unknown compound (UID).
212 From this comparison, we have observed that bright green-table olives contain 33-99% of Cu-metallo-
213 chlorophyll complexes, while Spanish table olives have approximately 95% of chlorophyll derivatives
214 without the magnesium porphyrin complex and approximately 5% of Cu-porphyrin complex.
215 Furthermore, bright green table olives contain small quantities of Mg-metallo-chlorophylls (0-8% due
216 to chlorophylls *a* and *b*) in contrast to Spanish table olives that do not contain detectable levels of
217 these compounds. The differences may be attributed to the different methods of the industrial
218 processing of table olives (Figure 9). The Castelvetro style (samples coded A and C) is manufactured
219 without fermentation and requires approximately 2 weeks for processing, although the shelf life of its
220 table olives is only a few weeks under warm storage conditions.²⁴ The presence of Mg-metallo-
221 chlorophylls (5-8%) in samples B and C implies that the processing style was Castelvetro. Sample A,
222 however, does not contain Mg-metallo-chlorophylls, which can be due to a modification of the
223 Castelvetro processing style to prolong the shelf life such as pasteurization. In contrast, the Spanish
224 style olive, based on a lactic fermentation process (Figure 9), requires 2-5 months^{24,25} and results in
225 the disappearance of chlorophylls *a* and *b* in less than 120 days.²⁶

226 Previous researchers^{10-12,27,28} have reported a GS alteration of the Gordal variety of table olives where
227 the color alteration is due to Cu-metallo-chlorophylls derivatives. One report shows the percent of
228 total Cu-metallo-chlorophylls a with respect to the total of a series after the lactic fermentation with
229 amounts ranging from 2% to 11%.²⁷ These data are lower than our observation for three commercially
230 available bright green table olive samples (36.1-99.8%).

231 We have found that the total elemental Cu from the quantification of Cu-metallo-chlorophyll
232 complexes present in the three bright green table olive samples varies between 1.3 mg and 4.7 mg/kg,
233 and within the range of mineral Cu (1.7-11.0 mg/ kg) quantified in different varietal table olives²⁹ and
234 fresh olives (3.5-7.2 mg/kg).³⁰ Thus, there appears to be adequate quantities of Cu native to the fruit
235 to allow for regreening to occur.¹⁰

236 The copper absorbed by the olive fruit could arise from copper in the soil but most likely derives from
237 the content of copper in the pesticides applied to prevent soapy olive (fungus infection by
238 *Gloeosporium olivarum*) and “repilo” (fungus infection by *Cycloconium oleaginum*).

239 As such, the bright green color of table olives is mostly due to the existence of Cu within porphyrin
240 ring, but the presence of Cu-metallo-chlorophylls has not been reported in fresh olives, fruits, or
241 leaves. However, these compounds can be generated using copper salts (CuCl₂, CuSO₄) during the
242 industrial processing of food⁴⁻⁷ or generated during the commercial processing of table olives with
243 endogenous copper absorbed by the fruit.²⁷ We assume that the Cu-chlorophyll compounds are
244 produced without adding copper salts and that the industrial processing has been carried out
245 according to international rules and regulations.^{31,32}

246 Olives with GS alteration might be a defect created by the partial formation of metallo-chlorophyll
247 pigments during the manufacture of green table olives resulting in a color that is not uniform.
248 Although color is important for consumer acceptance, the bright green table olives provide a source
249 of metallo-chlorophyll derivatives (Cu-Me-phytol-chlorin e₆, 26-48%; and Cu-pheophytin α , 3-18%)
250 that have been reported to possess an inhibitory activity against mutagenesis and higher antioxidant
251 activity as well.³³ Further investigation is needed to understand the processing method for regreening
252 table olives that will result in optimal uniformity in color and consumer acceptance.

253

254 AUTHOR INFORMATION

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347 FIGURE CAPTIONS:

348 Figure 1. Color measurement L*a*b* coordinates of five samples of table olives.

349 Figure 2. HPLC chromatograms of five samples, coded A-E, recorded at 650 nm.

350 Note: AU, absorption units; TO, table olives.

351 Figure 3. MS/MS daughter ions of Cu-15²-Me-phytol-rhodin g₇ ester.

352 Figure 4. MS/MS daughter ions of Cu-15²-Me-phytol-chlorin e₆ ester

353 Figure 5. MS/MS daughter ions of Cu-pheophytin *a*.

354 Figure 6. MS/MS daughter ions of Cu-pheophytin *a*'.

355 Figure 7. Percent of major pigments present in the five samples, coded A-E.

356 Note: Me-Pr g₇, 15²-Me-phytyl-rhodin g₇ ester; Cu-Me-Pr g₇, Cu-15²-Me-phytyl-rhodin g₇ ester; chl *b*, chlorophyll

357 *b*; Me-Pc e₆ ester, 15²-Me-phytyl-chlorin e₆ ester; Cu-Me-Pc e₆, Cu-15²-Me-phytyl-chlorin e₆ ester; chl *a*,

358 chlorophyll *a*; Pheo *b*, pheophytin *b*; Pheo *a*, pheophytin *a*; Cu-pheo *a*, Cu-pheophytin *a*; Cu-py *a*, Cu-

359 pyropheophytin *a*

360 Figure 8. Percents of total Cu-metallo-chlorophylls (T Cu), total Mg-metallo-chlorophylls (T Mg), total

361 chlorophylls without magnesium (T-Mg), and total Cu-metallo-chlorophylls plus Mg-metallo-

362 chlorophylls (T Cu+Mg) and the unknown peak (UID) for each sample studied.

363 Figure 9. Scheme of the three different processing styles for table olives. Note: Source, refs 24-25.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3.

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Figure 4

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Figure 5

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Figure 6

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Figure 7

Figure 8

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Figure 9

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Table 1. Gradient Used for Elution of Pigments by HPLC Reverse Phase^a

time (min)	solvent A	solvent B	solvent C	flow (mL/min)	curve
0.00	75.0	25.0	0.0	1.25	1
8.00	25.0	75.0	0.0	1.25	6
10.00	25.0	0.0	75.0	1.25	6
11.00	19.0	0.0	81.0	1.25	6
13.00	14.0	0.0	86.0	1.25	6
15.00	11.0	0.0	89.0	1.25	6
16.00	0.0	0.0	100.0	1.25	6
18.00	0.0	0.0	100.0	1.25	6
20.00	75.0	25.0	0.0	1.25	1

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399 NOTE: ^a (1/1/8) (v/v/v) water/ammonium acetate 1 M/methanol (solvent A), acetonitrile (solvent B), and reagent
400 alcohol (solvent C).

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Table 2. Different Structures of Pigments

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pigment	I. ring ^d	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M
pheophorbide <i>a</i>	1	H	CH ₃	H	COOCH ₃		2H
pyropheophorbide <i>a</i>	1	H	CH ₃	H	H		2H
Cu-pheophorbide <i>a</i>	1	H	CH ₃	H	COOCH ₃		Cu
Cu-pyropheophorbide <i>a</i>	1	H	CH ₃	H	H		Cu
15 ² -Me-phytyl-rhodin <i>g₇</i> ester	3	phytyl	CHO		CH ₂ COOCH ₃	COOH	2H
Cu-15 ² -Me-phytyl-rhodin <i>g₇</i> ester	3	phytyl	CHO		CH ₂ COOCH ₃	COOH	Cu
chlorophyll <i>b</i>	1	phytyl	CHO	H	COOCH ₃		Mg
15 ² -Me-phytyl-chlorin <i>e₆</i> ester	3	phytyl	CH ₃		CH ₂ COOCH ₃	COOH	2H
Cu-15 ² -Me-phytyl-chlorin <i>e₆</i> ester	3	phytyl	CH ₃		CH ₂ COOCH ₃	COOH	Cu
chlorophyll <i>a</i>	1	phytyl	CH ₃	H	COOCH ₃		Mg
pheophytin <i>b</i>	1	phytyl	CHO	H	COOCH ₃		2H
Cu-pheophytin <i>b</i>	1	phytyl	CHO	H	COOCH ₃		Cu
pyropheophytin <i>b</i>	1	phytyl	CHO	H	H		2H
Cu-pyropheophytin <i>b</i>	1	phytyl	CHO	H	H		Cu
pheophytin <i>a</i>	1	phytyl	CH ₃	H	COOCH ₃		2H
Cu-pheophytin <i>a</i>	1	phytyl	CH ₃	H	COOCH ₃		Cu
pyropheophytin <i>a</i>	1	phytyl	CH ₃	H	H		2H
15 ² -Me-phytyl-isochlorin <i>e₄</i>	3	phytyl	CH ₃		CH ₂ COOCH ₃	H	2H
15 ² -Et-phytyl-chlorin <i>e₄</i>	3	phytyl	CH ₃		CH ₂ CH ₃	COOH	2H
Cu-15 ² -Me-phytyl-isochlorin <i>e₄</i>	3	phytyl	CH ₃		CH ₂ COOCH ₃	H	Cu
Cu-15 ² -Et-phytyl-chlorin <i>e₄</i>	3	phytyl	CH ₃		CH ₂ CH ₃	COOH	Cu
Cu-pyropheophytin <i>a</i>	1	phytyl	CH ₃	H	H		Cu

^d I. ring: Isocyclic ring (ring V).

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407 Table 3. Spectroscopic and Chromatographic Information of Pigments Quantified by HPLC-MS and
408 Identified in the Samples^a

peak no.	pigment	K'_c	spectral data in the eluent				calcd ^c		obs ^d		published data				solvent	ref
			maxima (nm)				[M + H] ⁺	[M + H] ⁺	maxima (nm)							
			I	II	III	peak ratio			I	II	III	peak ratio				
1	pheophorbide <i>a</i>	2.05	410 ^b		666	1.94	593.276	593.277	409		666	1.85	MP	23		
2	Cu-pheophorbide <i>a</i>	2.76	400	425 ^b	651	1.10	654.190	654.193	400	424 ^b	654	1.00	MP	34		
3	pyropheophorbide <i>a</i>	3.27	410 ^b		666	2.03	535.270	535.272	409		666	1.85	MP	11		
4	Cu-pyropheophorbide <i>a</i>	4.63	400	425 ^b	651	1.10	596.184	596.182	404	422 ^b	653		MP	27		
5	unknown	9.14	447 ^b	577	626	10.98										
6	15 ² -Me-phytol-rhodin <i>g₇</i> ester	9.60	427 ^b	561	649	8.65	903.563	903.565	429 ^b		656		MP	21 ^f		
7	Cu-15 ² -Me-phytol-rhodin <i>g₇</i> ester	9.80	429 ^b	565	613	6.54	964.477	964.475	430 ^b		614		MP	21 ^f		
8	chlorophyll <i>b</i>	10.10	464 ^b	598	649	2.52	907.522	907.520	453 ^b	593	642	2.89	DE	35		
9	15 ² -Me-phytol-chlorin <i>e₆</i> ester	10.20	400 ^b		662	3.90	889.584	889.586	404 ^b	642	660		MP	21 ^f		
10	chlorophyll <i>b'</i>	10.35	464 ^b	598	649	2.52	907.522	907.520	453 ^b	593	642	2.89	DE	35		
11	Cu-15 ² -Me-phytol-chlorin <i>e₆</i> ester	10.65	407 ^b	504	629	2.46	950.498	950.495	408 ^b		635		MP	21 ^f		
12	chlorophyll <i>a</i>	10.95	432 ^b		662	1.14	893.543	893.545	430 ^b	615	661	1.32	DE	35		
13	chlorophyll <i>a'</i>	11.29	432 ^b		662	1.14	893.543	893.545	430 ^b	615	661	1.32	DE	35		
14	pheophytin <i>b</i>	11.73	437 ^b		651	4.59	885.552	885.550	433 ^b	599	654	4.81	DE	35		
15	Cu-pheophytin <i>b</i>	11.97	445 ^b		633	2.52	946.466	946.469	443 ^b		633	2.38	MP	34		
16	pheophytin <i>b'</i>	12.01	437 ^b		651	4.59	885.552	885.550	433 ^b	599	654	4.81	DE	35		
17	pyropheophytin <i>b</i>	12.35	437 ^b		651	4.34	827.547	827.549	435 ^b		654	3.83	MP	34		
18	pheophytin <i>a</i>	12.97	410 ^b	505	666	2.10	871.573	871.575	408 ^b	503	667	2.14	DE	35		
19	Cu-pyropheophytin <i>b</i>	13.12	444 ^b		633	2.02	888.461	888.463	443 ^b		633	2.38	MP	34		
20	15 ² -Me-phytol-isochlorin <i>e₄</i>	13.27	400 ^b		667	2.94	845.594	845.595	399 ^b		662	2.92	MP	27 ^f		
21	pheophytin <i>a'</i>	13.39	410 ^b	505	666	2.10	871.573	871.575	408 ^b	503	667	2.14	DE	35		
22	Cu-pheophytin <i>a</i>	13.91	400	425 ^b	651	0.97	932.487	932.489	400	424 ^b	654	1.00	MP	34		
23	Cu-pheophytin <i>a'</i>	14.57	400	425 ^b	651	0.97	932.487	932.489	400	424 ^b	654	1.00	MP	34		
24	pyropheophytin <i>a</i>	14.63	410 ^b	505	666	1.97	813.568	813.565	409 ^b		666	1.85	MP	34		
25	Cu-15 ² -Me-phytol-isochlorin <i>e₄</i>	15.50	408 ^b		630	2.34	906.508	906.510	406 ^b		630	2.55	MP	21 ^f		
26	Cu-pyropheophytin <i>a</i>	15.94	400	425 ^b	651	1.02	874.482	874.484	400	424 ^b	654	1.00	MP	34		

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410 NOTE: ^a $K'_c = (t_r - t_m)/t_m$, where t_r is the retention time of the peak and t_m is the retention time of the unretained
411 component. MP, mobile phase. DE, diethyl ether.412 ^b Soret band.413 ^c Calculated mass (the mass given is for the most abundant isotope, i.e., ⁶³Cu).414 ^d Observed mass, average Δ ppm < 2.5.415 ^e Compared to a similar structure without phytol.416 ^f Compared to formylpheophytin *a*.

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Table 4. MS/MS Fragmentation Pattern of Chlorophyll Derivatives

pigment	$(m/z)^a$		MS/MS (m/z)
	calculated ^b	observed	
15 ² -Me-phytol-rhodin g ₇ ester	901.5 a	901.5	857.6, 825.6, 507.2, 475.2
15 ² -Me-phytol-chlorin e ₆ ester	887.6 a	887.6	843.6, 811.6, 493.2, 461.2
Cu-15 ² -Me-phytol-rhodin g ₇ ester	962.5 a	962.5	918.5, 886.4, 568.2, 536.1
Cu-15 ² -Me-phytol-chlorin e ₆ ester	948.5 a	948.5	904.5, 872.5, 554.2, 522.1
Cu-pheophytin <i>b</i>	945.5 b	945.5	662.2, 590.1
Cu-pyropheophytin <i>b</i>	887.5 b	887.5	608.1, 564.2, 536.1
Cu-pheophytin <i>a</i>	931.5 b	931.5	652.2, 580.2, 576.2, 565.1
Cu-pheophytin <i>a'</i>	931.5 b	931.5	652.2, 580.2, 576.2, 565.1
Cu-pyropheophytin <i>a</i>	873.5 b	873.5	594.2, 550.2, 522.2

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421 NOTE: ^a [M-H]⁻ is labeled with "a" and [M]⁺ is labeled with "b".422 ^bThe mass given is for the most abundant isotope, that is, ⁶³Cu

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